

SITE GPR	YEAR 2010	AREA B	SECTOR	ELEVATION Min: 63.1812 Max: 63.3025	STRATIGRAPHICAL UNIT 1211 <input type="checkbox"/> Natural <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Anthropic	
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In cross-section? Yes No In elevation drawing? Yes No Photos: Yes No #: 735-737 Photo Model: Yes No #:

DEFINITION
Brown layer in roundish pit

Covered by SU: 1169 Fills SU: 1212 Filled by SU:

HOW IS LAYER DISTINGUISHED? Color Composition Compaction

FORMATION PROCESS
 Accumulation Construction Cutting Erosion Collapse Intentional deposition

INCLUSIONS For each inclusion specify frequency: (f)requent, (m)edium, (r)are

Anthropic	Geological	Organic	SOIL/MATRIX
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Pottery # <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Tiles # <input type="checkbox"/> Amphorae <input type="checkbox"/> Dolia <input type="checkbox"/> Mosaic tile(s) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Mortar m <input type="checkbox"/> Coins <input type="checkbox"/> Metal (specify) <input type="checkbox"/> Collapse debris <input type="checkbox"/> Glass	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Tufo (specify) m <input type="checkbox"/> Travertine <input type="checkbox"/> Other Limestone <input type="checkbox"/> Basalt <input type="checkbox"/> Clay <input type="checkbox"/> Sand <input type="checkbox"/> Silt <input type="checkbox"/> Pebbles (range) <input type="checkbox"/> Gravel (range)	<input type="checkbox"/> Charcoal <input type="checkbox"/> Ash <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Animal bones m <input type="checkbox"/> Human bones <input type="checkbox"/> Animal teeth <input type="checkbox"/> Human teeth <input type="checkbox"/> Shells <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)	clay ___% silt ___% sand ___% <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Granular <input type="checkbox"/> Layered <input type="checkbox"/> Cohesive Compaction: <input type="checkbox"/> Hard <input type="checkbox"/> Compact <input type="checkbox"/> Friable <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Loose <input type="checkbox"/> Soft Color: <input type="checkbox"/> Black <input type="checkbox"/> Brown <input type="checkbox"/> Gray <input type="checkbox"/> Light Brown <input type="checkbox"/> Light Gray <input type="checkbox"/> White <input type="checkbox"/> Yellow <input type="checkbox"/> Red <input type="checkbox"/> Light Yellow <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Other (specify) dark brown

UNIT LIMITS (also indicate on overlay)

Northern Limit Original Not Original Excavation Limit Depth: Original Not Original

Southern Limit Original Not Original Excavation Limit

Western Limit Original Not Original Excavation Limit

Eastern Limit Original Not Original Excavation Limit

STRATIGRAPHICAL SEQUENCE

Is equal to: _____ Is bound to (only for masonry): _____

Is abutted by: _____ Abuts: _____

Is covered by: 1169 Covers: _____

Is cut by: _____ Cuts: _____

Is filled by: _____ Fills: 1212

OBSERVATIONS Characteristics of this fill soil is similar to that of 1169. There were a number of inclusions, gravel, pottery, tiles and Amphorae.

DESCRIPTION
Position within sector: located in the westernmost section of Area B; adjacent to 1174.
Shape: Irregular, Polygon

For layers complete this section:
Surface (slope direction; visible inclusions): Pottery, tiles, mortar, small animal bones
Observations about inclusions (Clusters? Deposition slope): Inclusions were dispersed evenly throughout the fill.
Observations about thickness (Increases? Decreases?): Deepest in the center above bedrock; shallow above tufo floor
Nature of the interface with layer below: sharp diffuse commingled other (specify) covers tufo flooring and bedrock

For cuts complete this section:

Cut edges: rounded straight

Cut sides straight concave convex sloping

Cut bottom: flat concave irregular

How is cut top edge? sharp rounded

How is cut bottom edge? sharp rounded

Observations:

For structural remains complete this section

Alignment:

Building Technique: Adobe/Mud-brick Ashlar (blocks) irregular (unworked) stone Concrete Other (specify)

Binding Agent: None Clay Mortar (if so, specify composition, color, compaction)

Concrete inclusions:

Material Tufo Basalt Travertine Tiles Other (specify)
 Size Small (range) _____ Medium (range) _____ Large (range) _____ Representative size: e.g. 2 x 1 x 2 cmz

Wall Facing:

Opus quadratum Opus incertum Opus reticulatum Petit appareil Opus testaceum Opus mixtum Opus vittatum Other (specify)

Complete this section for foundations Faced foundation Wooden shuttering No shuttering

floor/revetment type

Floor type: Beaten Earth Opus signinum Opus scutulatum Opus Sectile Mosaic Opus spicatum Other (specify)

Wall finishing Stucco Opus signinum Plaster Painted Plaster Other (specify)

Approx. length, width, height of structural remains:

Description:

Sketch (if applicable, indicate North)

INTERPRETATION This soil was similar to 1169 in terms of color and inclusions. Because of this, it is difficult to say how much of the western cut it covers - but the sharp distinction between 1169 and the yellowish silt helps to establish a possible western extent, some distance before 1174.

SOIL SAMPLING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

NON SOIL SAMPLES: Yes No

If yes, specify (e.g. charcoal, mortar etc.):

Size:

SIEVING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

STRATIGRAPHICAL RELIABILITY

Good Fair Poor

*Contains 1169

Filled-out by	Demaine Francis	on	23-7-10
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